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1 **Evaluation of the impact of carbonaceous particles in the**
2 **mechanical performance of lipid Langmuir monolayers**

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11

12 **Abstract:** Carbonaceous particles are accounted among the most common environmental
13 pollutants. This makes necessary a careful examination of their potential impact on the physico-
14 chemical properties of different biological films, e.g. tear film, skin, or lung surfactant. This work
15 analyzes the interaction of three different types of carbonaceous particles with Langmuir
16 monolayers of 1,2-Dipalmitoyl-sn-glycerol-3-phosphocholine (DPPC) spread at the water/vapor
17 interface. This type of studies can be exploited as preliminary *in vitro* tests for evaluating the
18 potential risks and hazards of this type of pollutants for human health, which requires to study the
19 effect of the particles on the ability of lipid layers for reducing the surface tension under static and
20 dynamics conditions. The obtained results have shown that the insertion of particles into lipid films
21 leads to the emergence of excluded area-like effects which modify the interfacial cohesion and
22 packing. This hinders partially the ability of the lipid films for reducing the surface tension, which
23 may present important adverse effects for the normal physiological performance of lipid
24 membranes, and in particular for the performance of lung surfactant layers. Furthermore, the
25 analysis of the response of lipid layers including carbonaceous particles against mechanical stresses
26 also evidenced that particle incorporation worsens the mechanical performance of lipid layers,
27 which may alter both their functional and structural roles.

28 **Keywords:** lipid films; carbon nanoparticles; fluid interfaces; model systems; protection; surface
29 tension; monolayers; rheological properties

30 Introduction

31 The progressive increase of the injection of pollutants into the atmosphere as result of the
32 combustion processes of fossil fuels in industries, power plants and vehicles, and the development
33 of the nanotechnology, and its associated industries, makes necessary to explore the potential
34 harmful effects of such compounds for human health, and in particular their impact over the
35 stability and physiological performance of the first protection barriers of human body constituted
36 for different structures formed mainly by lipids (tear film, skin or lung surfactant) [1].

37 The physiological impact of the interaction of particles and lipid layers continues being subjected to
38 a strong controversy [2-4]. Particles are commonly associated with pathogenesis and the
39 development of different respiratory diseases, including asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary
40 diseases, fibrosis, or lung cancer [5-12]. Furthermore, the World Health Organization (WHO)
41 statistics ascribe one third of the deaths caused by strokes, lung cancer, or cardiac diseases to the air
42 pollution [13]. On the other side, particles are widespread in different areas of the nanomedicine,
43 e.g. drug delivery or theranosis [14-16]. Therefore, it is clear that the analysis of the potential adverse
44 effects of particles for human health deserves further attention. However, the direct evaluation of
45 the effect of particles using *in vivo* assays is very difficult because they require the use of very
46 invasive methodologies, and hence it is necessary to design methodologies for a preliminary
47 evaluation of the potential risks and hazards associated with particles, using model systems [17-20].
48 The studies based on model systems may provide very valuable information for assessing the
49 molecular bases of the effect induced for particles in different protective lipid layers, which plays a
50 key role on the design of particles for biomedical applications and the mitigation of their potential
51 toxicity.

52 The use of models based on Langmuir monolayers spread at the water/vapor interface has been
53 established from many years as very powerful tools for a preliminary evaluation of the impact of
54 different chemicals, both molecular and supramolecular species, on the organization and properties
55 of layers mimicking some relevant features of different biological systems, commonly lipid-based
56 structures but not limited [21-30]. Nevertheless, Langmuir monolayers consider only a single layer
57 which is an oversimplification of the true biophysical picture occurring *in vivo* because most of the
58 biological structures, and in particular those based in the assembly of lipids, are complex
59 supramolecular architectures [19,25]. Therefore, the studies based on the use of Langmuir
60 monolayers can provide information about certain molecular details of the interaction of different
61 chemicals with minimal systems, e.g. single cellular membrane leaflets, or the lung surfactant film
62 trapped at the interface between the aqueous layer overlying the alveolar cavity and the gas
63 contained within such cavity [2,18,26,27]. However, these studies neglect the role of specific
64 hydrodynamics and aerodynamics aspects guiding the interaction of particles with lipid barriers
65 under *in vivo* conditions. Thus, the necessity of a dispersing medium, commonly a volatile organic
66 solvent, for spreading the material, both the lipids and the particles, at the water/vapor interface
67 and ensuring its homogenous distribution may affect both the interaction between particles and
68 lipids, and the packing of the molecules at the interface. This is a very important aspect because it
69 has been recently reported that the methodology used for the deposition of the particles at the fluid
70 interface may lead to strong modifications of their interactions with lipid layers [31]. Furthermore,
71 the use of Langmuir films makes difficult to mimic the specific mass transport boundary conditions
72 which can modify the interaction between particles and the biomimetic layers [32,33].

73 This work is aimed to elucidate the effect of different types of carbonaceous particles, used as model
74 of environmental pollutants, on the mechanical performance of Langmuir monolayers of 1,2-
75 Dipalmitoyl-sn-glycerol-3-phosphocholine (DPPC). The choice of DPPC as model is not arbitrary,

and is supported on the prevalence of this lipid or other analogous in most of the lipid structures and membranes of mammals, e.g. DPPC accounts for 40wt% of the composition of the lung surfactant in mammals [2,18,20,30,34-40]. It is true that the interaction of different carbonaceous nanomaterials with lipid layers have been widely studied in recent years [41-48]. However, up to date there are no systematic studies including a comparison of the effect of different types of carbonaceous particles on the interfacial behavior of lipid films, and in particular on their mechanical performance. The latter is especially important when lung surfactant layers are considered [2, 20]. It is well-known that any modification of the rheological properties of lung surfactant films can increase the respiratory work, which may induce a premature alveolar collapse and hence the emergence of acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) or other dysfunctions of the normal respiratory function [2]. Therefore, it is expected that the results contained in this work may contribute to deepen on the understanding of the most fundamental bases underlying the impact of carbonaceous nanomaterials on the performance of lipid layers.

Materials and Methods

Chemicals. 1,2-Dipalmitoyl-sn-glycerol-3-phosphocholine (DPPC), with a molecular weight of 734.1 g/mol, was purchased from Avanti Polar Lipids, Inc. (Alabaster, AL, USA) at 99.9% purity, and used as received. Three different carbonaceous particles were used as pollutant models: (a) carbon soot particles (C_{Soot}) supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (Saint Louis, MO, USA) [49], and (b) two different types of carbon particles derived from combustion processes of ethylene (C_{Eth}) and benzene (C_{Ben}), which were gifted [50-53]. Details of some relevant physico-chemical characteristic of the used carbonaceous particles can be found in the Supporting Material (Table S.1). Further details on the particle characterization can be found in the works by Santini et al. [49,50].

Chloroform (CHROMASOLV™, for High Performance Liquid Chromatography, stabilized with ethanol) purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Saint Louis, MO, USA) was used for preparing the spreading solutions of DPPC and the dispersions of carbon particles.

Ultrapure deionized water for cleaning and experiments was obtained by a multi-cartridge purification system Elix + Milli-Q (Millipore, Burlington, MA, USA). This water presents a resistivity higher than 18 MΩ·cm, a total organic content lower than 6 ppm and a surface tension around 72 mN/m at 22 °C without evidence of surface tension kinetics were found for the used water over several hours. The pH of the water was around 6.5, and no salts were used for fixing the ionic strength.

Preparation of Langmuir monolayers. Lipid monolayers were spread at the water/vapor interface by dropping controlled volumes of DPPC from its solution in chloroform (concentration about 1 mg/mL or 1.36 mM) using a high-precision Hamilton syringe (Hamilton Company, Reno, NV, USA). This methodology ensures the control of the interfacial density of DPPC, Γ , upon solvent evaporation. The initial interfacial density of DPPC spread at the water/vapor interface Γ_0 was fixed in all the experiments in a value of 1.7 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2$, corresponding to an area per molecule of about 98 Å^2 .

The preparation of the mixed monolayers was done following a two-step approach: (i) a DPPC monolayer was obtained from the spreading at the pristine water/vapor interface of the lipid from its solution in chloroform (concentration 1 mg/mL), and (ii) a given amount of the particle dispersion (concentration 1 mg/mL) was spread onto the preformed DPPC monolayer, again using chloroform as spreading solvent (Notice that particle dispersions were sonicated during 15 min using a laboratory ultrasound bath to minimize their aggregation before their spreading at the interface).

120 This procedure allows obtaining monolayers with specific DPPC: particles weight ratio at the
121 interface. Once monolayers including particles and DPPC are obtained, it is necessary to wait during
122 1 h before starting the experiments to ensure a complete evaporation of the solvent and, in the case
123 of mixed monolayers for ensuring that the equilibrium of the composite system driven by the
124 nanoparticle–lipid interactions is reached [35,44,48]. It is worth noting that the monolayers prepared
125 following the above discussed approach cannot be considered as true mixed monolayer because
126 they were not obtained after the spreading of a mixed dispersion containing the DPPC and the
127 particles (first, the DPPC is spread at the pure water/vapor interface, and then the addition of the
128 particles is made onto the preformed DPPC monolayer). However, for simplicity the term mixed
129 monolayers will be used, along the manuscript, for monolayers involving DPPC and carbonaceous
130 particles.

131 The temperature was fixed at 22.0 ± 0.1 °C in all the experiments. Even though this temperature is
132 far from the physiological one (37 °C), the main conclusions obtained in our study may be
133 extrapolated, at least from a semi-quantitative perspective, to physiological conditions. This may be
134 understood considering that the phase transition of DPPC appears above the physiological
135 temperature, and only a shift of the phase behavior with the temperature is expected, without any
136 significant impact on the main physico-chemical insights extracted from the experimental results
137 [54]. Furthermore, the use of a low temperature makes easier to tune the phase of DPPC monolayers
138 by compression-expansion of the interfacial area using lateral barriers, which makes possible to
139 explore the effect of particles in the several 2D phases encountered in a biological membrane (fluid
140 and packed).

141 It is worth mentioning that the properties of the mixed monolayers obtained upon chloroform
142 evaporation will be affected by the conditions in which DPPC and particles are mixed as was
143 recently demonstrated by Miguel-Diez et al. [31]. This work has used a methodology for the
144 preparation of the mixed layers where the interaction between particles and lipid layers occurs only
145 at the water/vapor interface. This methodology was chosen because it provides a good approach to
146 that what happens during the deposition of pollutants on lipid layers (skin or tear film) or during
147 the inhalation of particles and their subsequent incorporation into the lung surfactant film.

148 **Experimental.** All the experiments were performed using a commercial Langmuir trough KSV
149 Nima model KN2002 (Biolin Scientific, Espoo, Finland), equipped with two Delrin® barriers
150 allowing for symmetric compression/expansion of the free liquid surface. This allows studying
151 Langmuir monolayers under equilibrium and dynamic conditions. The total surface area of the
152 teflon trough is 243 cm². The surface tension, γ , was measured using a force balance fitted with a
153 paper Wilhelmy plate (Whatman CHR1 chromatography paper, effective perimeter 20.6 mm,
154 supplied by Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA), ensuring a zero contact angle. The surface
155 pressure, Π , is obtained as the difference between the surface tension of the pure water/vapor
156 interface γ_w and γ , i.e. $\Pi = \gamma_w - \gamma$.

157 *Surface Pressure – Area Isotherms.* For obtaining the Π -A isotherms of the Langmuir monolayers, the
158 surface pressure was measured during the compression - expansion of the free area of the
159 monolayer, at a fixed velocity of 2 cm²/min. which is equivalent to a compression rate $R \approx 3 \times 10^{-5}$ s⁻¹.
160 The use of this velocity in the experiments allows minimizing the emergence of undesired non-
161 equilibrium effect in the obtained isotherms [55-59]. Compression was started after one hour from
162 the solution deposition. This time was checked to be long enough for ensuring the complete
163 evaporation of the solvent and the achievement of the equilibrium of the composite system, driven

164 by the interaction between the carbonaceous particles and the lipid molecules at the water/vapor
165 interface.

166 *Oscillatory Barrier experiments.* The Langmuir trough can be also utilized for evaluating the response
167 of interfacial layers upon dilational deformations by measuring the surface pressure response to
168 harmonic oscillatory variations of the interfacial area, A , at controlled amplitude, $\Delta A/A_0$, and a fixed
169 deformation frequency, ν [60,61]. The change of the interfacial area can be defined as

$$A(t) = A_0 + \Delta A \sin(2\pi\nu t). \quad (1)$$

170 The change of the interfacial area (strain) leads to a stress response $\Delta\Pi = \Pi_0 - \Pi(t)$, which is defined as
171 the change of surface pressure between the reference state Π_0 and the instantaneous value of the
172 surface pressure $\Pi(t)$. For deformations with a small amplitude, i.e. for deformations remaining
173 within the linear regime, the stress response also follows a sinusoidal profile with the same
174 frequency than the deformation

$$\Pi(t) = \Delta\Pi \sin(2\pi\nu t + \phi) \quad (2)$$

175 with ϕ being a phase shift accounting for a possible delay of the stress response (surface pressure
176 change) in relation to the strain (area deformation). For systems with linear response, the stress can
177 be considered proportional to the deformation $u(t) = \Delta A/A_0$ (elastic term) and to the rate of
178 deformation $du(t)/dt$ (viscous term), which allows one to write the stress as

$$\Pi(t) = \varepsilon' u(t) + \kappa \left(\frac{du(t)}{dt} \right), \quad (3)$$

179 with ε' and κ being the dilational elasticity and viscosity, respectively. Considering the definition
180 given by Equation (3) and assuming a generic harmonic perturbation, the complex dilational
181 viscoelasticity, ε , can be defined as

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon' + 2\pi\nu\kappa i, \quad (4)$$

182 with $i = \sqrt{-1}$, so that $E = |\varepsilon|$. The analysis of the curves corresponding to the strain and stress in
183 terms of Equations (1) and (2) provide information about their amplitudes and the phase shift,
184 enabling for the calculation of the dilational viscoelasticity.

185 It should be noted that under dilational deformations with amplitude above a threshold value, the
186 emergence of distortions in the response function is common, which is associated with a weakening
187 of the linearity of the mechanical response of the film which means that the response is no longer
188 linear [62,63]. The analysis of the response beyond the linear regime can be effectively done by using
189 Fourier Transform (FFT) of the surface pressure response. This leads to the emergence of peaks
190 corresponding to overtones of the characteristic deformation frequency in the Fourier spectrum [64].

191 Results

192 **Analysis of the particle incorporation into DPPC monolayers.** The evaluation of the incorporation
193 of carbonaceous particles into DPPC monolayers, and their potential impact on the mechanical
194 performance of such films was performed by adding different amounts of nanoparticles from their
195 dispersions in chloroform to the DPPC monolayer already spread on the surface of pure water. It
196 should be noted that the characterization of the surface pressure (Π)-area (A) isotherms for
197 carbonaceous particles directly spread at the water/vapor interface was performed before the

198 analysis of the incorporation of particles into the DPPC layers (see Figure S.1 in Supporting
199 Material).

200 Figure 1 displays the surface pressure-area per lipid molecule isotherms (Π - A isotherms. It should
201 be noted that the areas are shown normalized for a reference value A_0 corresponding to the
202 maximum area accessible per lipid molecule just after the spreading of the monolayer at the
203 interface. Thus, the isotherms in Figure 1 are depicted as Π - A/A_0 representations) obtained for DPPC
204 monolayers upon the incorporation of amounts (weight fractions, x_p) of the different carbonaceous
205 particles studied in this work. From the Π - A/A_0 isotherms is possible to obtain information related
206 to the impact of the incorporation of the carbonaceous particles on the phase behavior and the lateral
207 packing of the lipid molecules at the water/vapor interface. It should be noted that even though the
208 information extracted from the isotherms does not have a direct correlation to the biophysical
209 performance of the lipids films, they provide a semi-quantitative evaluation of the impact of the
210 incorporation of the particles in the organization of the lipid molecules, and allow the
211 understanding of some fundamental aspects of the lipid-particle interactions.

212

213 **Figure 1.** Π - A/A_0 isotherms for DPPC Langmuir monolayers upon the incorporation of different weight fractions
214 of particles at the interface (x_p): C_{soot} (a), C_{Eth} (b) and C_{Ben} . Each curve corresponds to DPPC monolayers with a
215 different weight fraction of particles at the interface (x_p): (■) 0.00, (■) 0.10, (■) 0.33, and (■) 0.75. The results were
216 obtained from the average of three individual experiments with a standard deviation smaller than 5%.

217 The isotherm of DPPC spread at the bare water/vapor displays the typical features expected for the
218 monolayers of this lipid according to the literature [55-59]. This allows one to define three
219 characteristic regions for DPPC monolayers as function of the compression degree, i.e. the value of
220 A/A_0 (Note: the higher the value of A/A_0 the smaller the compression degree). For monolayers with the
221 smallest compression degree, corresponding to the gas and liquid expanded (LE) phases, the
222 reduction of the area leads to a mild increase of the surface pressure associated with the increase of
223 the interfacial density (Note: the number of the molecules remains constant but the area available is reduced
224 by the compression) and the reorientation of the molecules at the fluid interface. This proceeds until
225 a threshold value of the interfacial density, which defines the onset of the coexistence region of
226 DPPC monolayers, is reached. This coexistence region is evidenced by the emergence of a quasi-flat
227 region (pseudo-plateau) in the isotherm characterized by a vanishing change of the surface pressure
228 with the increase of the compression degree, which may be explained considering that the
229 reorientation of the DPPC molecules at the water/vapor interface drives the transition from a
230 disordered LE phase to a more ordered one (liquid compressed, LC). One the LE-LC phase

231 coexistence region is overcome, the reduction of the area available for the monolayer, i.e. the
232 increase of the packing density, leads to a sharp increase of the surface pressure within the LC
233 expanded and solid phases until the rupture of the monolayer at the collapse surface pressure, Π_c .
234 It should be noted that the compression of DPPC monolayers leads to highly condensed states with
235 very high values of surface pressure (quasi-null surface tensions). This ability for reducing the
236 surface tension ($\Pi = \gamma_0 - \gamma$, with γ_0 and γ being the surface tensions of the bare water/vapor interface
237 and the interface in presence of the surface active materials, respectively) of DPPC monolayers
238 presents a very important biophysical implication for the correct physiological function of many
239 lipid layers, e.g. lung surfactant and their resistance upon mechanical disturbances. Therefore, any
240 change on the ability for reducing the surface tension of DPPC layers may impact decisively on the
241 normal physiological function of lipid layers.

242 The incorporation of carbonaceous particles into the DPPC monolayers leads to three different
243 modifications on the surface pressure-area isotherm in relation to that what was found for pure
244 lipid monolayers spread at the water/vapor interface: (i) modification of the isotherm shape,
245 reflected in the disappearance of the LE-LC coexistence plateau; (ii) shifting of the isotherm to higher
246 values of A/A_0 , i.e. to more expanded states (higher values of the reduced area), and (iii) reduction
247 of the maximum surface pressure that the monolayer can attain upon compression, i.e. the collapse
248 pressure. The modification of the shape of the isotherm may be explained as a result of the
249 modification of the reorientation mechanism of the lipid molecules within the fluid interface. This
250 may be understood considering that particles are obstacles that limit the mobility of the particles
251 and the interaction balance within the interface, and hence lipid molecules cannot undergo a LE-LC
252 phase transition through a coexistence region [55]. It should be stressed that all the experiments
253 were performed under the same conditions, which makes possible to assume that the disappearance
254 of the flat LE-LC plateau appears as a result of the direct interaction between particles and lipid
255 molecules. On the other side, the shift of the isotherm to higher values of the reduced area can be
256 explained assuming that particles incorporated within the interface occupy part of the area available
257 for the lipid molecules, acting as an obstacle, which leads to an earlier lifting-off of the LE phase of the
258 DPPC monolayers. This means that particles induce an excluded-area like effect on the isotherm
259 which leads to the DPPC monolayer to a situation in which they behave in such a way that appears
260 reminiscent from that expected for a monolayer with a higher interfacial density [65]. This excluded
261 area-like effect appears very similar independently of the type of particles considered, having a clear
262 dependence on the x_p value. This can be understood considering that the increase of interfacial
263 density of particles leads to a stronger reduction of the area available for the DPPC molecules, and
264 the increase of the total interfacial concentration of the monolayer.

265 A more detailed analysis of the dependences of the changes of the DPPC isotherm on x_p evidences
266 that the dose dependent modification of the isotherm is strongly dependent on the specific type of
267 the particles incorporated into the monolayer. Therefore, it can be assumed that the impact of
268 particles is not only related to the area exclusion effect, and according to previous studies by Bykov
269 et al. [66], the role of the different particle size may be also neglected. This makes necessary to
270 analyze the role of the interactions between the different components forming the mixed layer
271 (particle-particle, lipid-lipid and particle-lipid). These interactions modify the lateral packing of
272 the lipid molecules within the interface, as well as the aggregation and distribution of the particles.
273 The incorporation of C_{Soot} and C_{Ben} into DPPC monolayers leads to a clear dose-dependent shift of
274 the isotherm to higher values of the area reduced, whereas the shift of the isotherm appears rather
275 independent on the x_p value upon the incorporation of C_{Eth} . This suggests a different distribution of
276 the carbonaceous particles within the interface. The dose-dependent shift of the isotherm found for

277 DPPC monolayers with C_{Soot} and C_{Ben} may be explained considering that the increase of x_p enhances
 278 the area exclusion effects. This is only possible considering that C_{Soot} and C_{Ben} are incorporated within
 279 the interface forming pseudo-2D aggregates which tends to occupy the maximum area available,
 280 similarly to that what was reported for the incorporation of fumed silica particles [35]. On the other
 281 side, the absence of a dose-dependent behavior upon the incorporation of C_{Eth} into DPPC
 282 monolayers suggests that the incorporation of these particles leads to the formation of a 3D particle-
 283 stackings which does not modify significantly the area occupied by the particles, and in turn leads
 284 to a situation in which the area exclusion is not affected by the change of the x_p . The formation of
 285 this out-of-plane structures (wrinkles, folds, or buckles) upon the incorporation of carbonaceous
 286 particles into DPPC monolayers leads to a lower effective interfacial density of particles at the
 287 interface than that what is expected considering the x_p value as was previously reported in DPPC
 288 monolayers upon the incorporation of carbon black particles, fullerenes and graphene oxide
 289 nanosheets [44,47,67]. The above results suggest that even though all particles present carbonaceous
 290 origin, subtle differences on their chemistry may impact on their aggregation and distribution
 291 within the lipid monolayer.
 292 The above discussion have so far presented the effect of each type of particles on the behavior of
 293 DPPC monolayers. However, it can be interesting to perform a combined analysis of the effect of
 294 the different types of particles for a fixed value of the weight fraction of incorporated particles.
 295 Figure 2a displays the Π - A/A_0 isotherms for a pristine DPPC monolayer and DPPC monolayers
 296 upon the incorporation of a fixed amount of the different types of carbonaceous particles (Notice
 297 that the results for other weight fractions of particles appear very similar to those reported in Figure
 298 2a).

299

300 **Figure 2.** (a) Π - A/A_0 isotherms for DPPC Langmuir monolayers upon the incorporation of different types of
 301 carbonaceous particles as a fixed $x_p=0.33$. Each curve corresponds to DPPC monolayers with a different type of
 302 carbonaceous particles: (■) No particles, (■) C_{Soot} , (■) C_{Eth} , and (■) C_{Ben} . (b) Dependence of the collapse pressure, Π_c , on
 303 x_p for DPPC monolayers upon the incorporation of (■) C_{Soot} , (■) C_{Eth} , and (■) C_{Ben} . Note that the lines are guides for the
 304 eyes. (c) Dependence of $(A/A_0)_{\text{lim}}$ on x_p for DPPC monolayers upon the incorporation of (■) C_{Soot} , (■) C_{Eth} , and (■) C_{Ben} .
 305 Note that the lines are guides for the eyes. Notice that the results were obtained from the average of three individual
 306 experiments with a standard deviation smaller than 5%.

307 The incorporation of different types of carbonaceous particles into the DPPC monolayers induces
308 different modifications in the isotherm of the lipid at the bare water/vapor interface. Thus, even
309 though the three type of particles considered are hydrophobic and have a carbonaceous origin, the
310 subtle differences on their surface chemistry and morphology which modify the aggregation of the
311 particles and their dispersion within the interface affects to the interaction operating within the
312 interface, and, as matter of fact, to the organization of particles and lipids at the interface [68]. This
313 leads to two well differentiated regions in relation to the modification of the phase behavior of DPPC
314 monolayers as result of the incorporation of carbonaceous particles. At low values of the
315 compression degree, the steric hindrance associated with the specific distribution of each type of
316 particles within the interface appears as a critical parameter on the control of the packing of the lipid
317 molecules at the interface. On the other side, at high values of the compression degree, the packing
318 of the molecules starts to be mainly controlled for the hydrophobic interactions between the
319 carbonaceous particles and the tails of the lipid molecules, which makes that the maximum surface
320 pressure reached by the monolayers becomes rather independent of the type of particles
321 incorporated within the DPPC monolayer. On the basis of the above results, it is possible to assume
322 that the impact of the particles on the organization of the lipid within the monolayers is the result
323 of an intricate balance between the excluded area effects, the steric hindrance, and different types
324 of interactions resulting from the specific chemistry of the particles.

325 The detailed analysis of the impact of the incorporation of particles in the feature of the isotherm
326 provides a first quantitative parameter which gives information about the worsening of the
327 mechanical performance of the DPPC monolayer. Thus, the analysis of the change of the collapse
328 pressure, Π_c , as result of the particle incorporation give information of the maximum surface
329 pressure that the monolayer can reach before its rupture, which informs about the lateral packing
330 of the monolayer component. Figure 2b displays the dependence of the Π_c on x_p for DPPC
331 monolayers upon incorporation of different types of carbonaceous particles. This representation
332 quantifies the viability of the lipid for decreasing the surface tension upon incorporation of particles,
333 providing a first evaluation of their mechanical resistance, i.e. the reduction of surface pressure
334 indicates a premature monolayer collapse. The reduction of the ability of DPPC for reducing the
335 surface tension upon compression as result of the incorporation of particles may be associated with
336 the emergence of a respiratory dysfunction associated with inhaled particles. Thus, the reduction of
337 the surface pressure of DPPC monolayers can be equivalent to an increase of the work required
338 during the respiratory cycle [2].

339 The results evidence that the incorporation of particles decreases the maximum surface pressure
340 that DPPC monolayers can reach before its rupture, which is an indication of the irreversible
341 character of the incorporation of particles. This evidences that the incorporation of particles hinders
342 the formation of highly condensed phases in DPPC monolayers. This may be rationalized
343 considering the importance of the lateral hydrophobic cohesive interactions in the packing at the
344 interface when the degree of compression is high. Thus, in DPPC monolayers at the bare
345 water/vapor, the lateral cohesive interactions are strong, which allows the formation of close packed
346 monolayers with a high Π_c . On the other side, the introduction of carbonaceous particles leads to
347 the emergence of heterogeneities within the monolayer, which weaken the average cohesion within
348 the monolayer in relation to pure DPPC monolayers. This can be understood in terms of the steric
349 hindrance induced by the particles, which modifies the interfacial packing in relation to that what
350 is found in pure DPPC monolayer, and, in turn modify the cohesion on the layer. On the other side,
351 as was mentioned above, the specific type of carbonaceous particles does not influence the
352 dependence of the collapse surface pressure on the weight fraction of incorporated particles, and

353 only slight modifications as function of the specific nature of the carbonaceous particles are found.
 354 Therefore, the incorporation of hydrophobic particles, independently of their nature, leads to a
 355 reduction of the strength of the average cohesion interactions within the interface, which is the result
 356 of the heterogeneities on the lateral organization emerging within the film. It should be noted that
 357 the presence of hydrophobic interactions between the particles and the tails of DPPC molecules
 358 makes very difficult the composition refinement of the monolayer upon compression, and hence
 359 the ability of DPPC monolayers for reducing the surface tension is partially inactivated. This may
 360 be a very important contribution to the inactivation of lung surfactant upon deposition of inhaled
 361 particles [29].

362 A better quantification of the steric hindrance to the lipid packing as result of the particle
 363 incorporation can be obtained from the values of area limit, $(A/A_0)_{lim}$, estimated by the extrapolation
 364 of the steepest, high pressure, linear part of the $\Pi - A/A_0$ curve to zero surface pressure. This
 365 parameter gives information related to the maximum packing of the monolayer before its collapse
 366 [69]. Figure 2c displays the dependence of $(A/A_0)_{lim}$ on x_p for DPPC monolayers upon the
 367 incorporation of different types of carbonaceous particles. The increase of $(A/A_0)_{lim}$ on x_p evidences
 368 the reduction of the packing of the monolayers as carbonaceous particles are incorporated. This
 369 agrees with the above discussed weakening of the cohesion of the monolayer at the liquid/vapor
 370 interface. It should be noted that the specific characteristic of the particles presents a strong impact
 371 on the reduction of the interfacial packing, which may be again correlated to the different
 372 aggregation of particles at the interface. Thus, the higher the area expansion associated with particle
 373 incorporation the more homogenous the particle distribution within the interface. This may be
 374 understood considering that subtle differences on the interaction between lipid molecules and
 375 carbonaceous particles at the interface may lead to different changes on the contact angle of the
 376 carbonaceous particles at the interface, and consequently to modifications in the aggregation
 377 pathways of the particles [67]. This leads to a situation where C_{Soot} and C_{Ben} appear distributed
 378 within the whole DPPC monolayer, reducing the lipid-lipid cohesion interaction, and C_{Eth} appears
 379 incorporated as big aggregates that leads only to a local distortion of the lipid cohesion, and hence
 380 their weakening of the lateral packing of the monolayer is more limited. Similar results were found
 381 in our previous publication when the incorporation of silica particles and carbon black particles into
 382 DPPC monolayers was analyzed [48].

383 **Thermodynamics analysis of the interaction between DPPC and carbonaceous particles.** The Π -
 384 A/A_0 isotherms have provided important insights on the effect of the interfacial interaction between
 385 particles and DPPC molecules in the organization and packing of the molecules at the interface.
 386 Further details about the impact of such interaction can be obtained by analyzing the isotherms in
 387 terms of the thermodynamic of mixtures [70,71]. This defines the average area occupied for a
 388 molecule in absence of any interactions for a mixture of two species, A_{ideal} , as

$$A_{ideal} = x_{DPPC} A_{DPPC} + x_p A_p, \quad (5)$$

389 where A_{DPPC} and A_p are the areas per molecule in pure monolayers of DPPC and carbon particles,
 390 respectively, at the considered Π , and x_{DPPC} and x_p the weight fractions of DPPC and carbon particles
 391 in the mixture, respectively. The deviations of the behavior of the experimental system from that
 392 expected for an ideal mixture can be understood in terms of the interactions occurring within the
 393 monolayer. These can be accounted by introducing the average excess area, A_{exc} , defined as follows

$$A_{exc} = A_{I2} - A_{ideal}, \quad (6)$$

394 where A_{12} is the average area per molecule in the mixed monolayer at a given value of Π . For an
 395 ideal mixed monolayer, A_{exc} is zero. Figure 3 shows the A_{exc} values for the DPPC monolayers as a
 396 function of the weight fraction of carbon particles incorporated.

397
 398 **Figure 3.** Representation of A_{exc} as a function of the weight fraction of nanoparticles in the mixed monolayer for
 399 different types of carbon particles under different degree of compression, i.e. different values of the surface
 400 pressure (Π): C_{Soot} (a), C_{Eth} (b) and C_{Ben} . Each curve corresponds to different values of the surface pressure (Π): (■)
 401 7.5 mN/m, (■) 11 mN/m, (■) 20 mN/m and (■) 30 mN/m. The lines are guides for the eyes, and the results were
 402 obtained from the average of three individual experiments with a standard deviation smaller than 5%.

403 The incorporation of carbon particles into DPPC monolayers leads to mixed films with a positive
 404 value A_{exc} independently of the chemical nature of the particles and their weight fraction. This
 405 indicates that the combination of excluded area effects and hydrophobic interactions leads to the
 406 emergence of repulsive interactions between particles and lipid molecules.

407 The dependences of the A_{exc} on the weight fraction changes as function of the type of carbonaceous
 408 particle incorporated into DPPC monolayers and the analyzed surface pressure. Thus, the
 409 incorporation of C_{Ben} into DPPC monolayers leads for the highest values of the surface pressure to
 410 two different regimes for the dependences of A_{exc} on the weight fraction of particles. The first regime
 411 is characterized by the growth of A_{exc} with the weight fraction of particles incorporated into the
 412 monolayer. This makes possible to consider that the importance of the cohesive interactions in this
 413 compositional range is rather limited, and hence the main driving force governing the packing and
 414 orientation of the lipid molecules at the interface emerges from the excluded area effect associated
 415 with the incorporation of the particles. Beyond a threshold value of the weight fraction of particles
 416 (around 0.2-0.4), the A_{exc} decreases with the increase of the weight fraction of particles. This may be
 417 understood considering that the high interfacial density of carbon particles at the fluid interface
 418 enhances the interactions between the lipid tails and the carbon particles, with these hydrophobic
 419 interactions competing with the non-favorable excluded-area effect. It should be stressed that even
 420 though the importance of the attractive interactions between lipid molecules and carbon particles
 421 increases, the excluded area effects are dominant on the control of the packing of the molecules
 422 within the entire range of interfacial compositions. On the other side, the values of A_{exc} upon the
 423 incorporation of C_{Soot} and C_{Eth} , and for the lowest surface pressures upon the incorporation of C_{Ben} ,
 424 follow a monotonous decrease with the weight fraction of particles, i.e., the dependence of A_{exc} on
 425 the particle weight fraction shows only the above called second regime.

426 Moreover, the results evidence a decrease in the value of A_{exc} with the increase of compression
 427 degree, i.e. Π . This results from an increase of the cohesive interactions between lipids and particles,
 428 which is reasonable considering the reduction of the available area at the interface and the increase
 429 of the proximity between particles and lipid molecules. It should be noted that the results evidence
 430 a strong decrease in the values of A_{exc} as the lipids pass from the LE phase (7.5 and 11 mN/m) to the
 431 LC phase (20 and 30 mN/m). This can be explained considering the different strength of the
 432 hydrophobic interactions between the tails of the lipids and particles. Thus, whereas lipids in the
 433 LC phase are mostly oriented perpendicularly to the interface, presenting the entire tail for
 434 interacting with the particles which enhances the packing of the interface, lipids in the LE phase are
 435 mainly placed with their tails oriented parallel to the interface which minimizes their interactions
 436 with the particles.

437 **Hysteresis upon compression-expansion deformations of the monolayer.** Physiologically relevant
 438 processes involving lipid layers present a dynamics character. This makes important to evaluate
 439 how the incorporation of particles into DPPC monolayers modify the whole compression-expansion
 440 cycle. Figure 4a shows the dependence of the surface pressure on A/A_0 during the whole
 441 compression–expansion cycle of the interfacial area of a monolayer of DPPC upon the incorporation
 442 of carbonaceous particles.

443 **Figure 4. (a)** Compression–expansion hysteresis cycle for DPPC monolayer containing C_{Eth} ($x_p = 0.33$). **(b)** Dependence
 444 of the normalized hysteresis area referred to that corresponding of pure DPPC monolayers spread at the water/vapor
 445 interface, HA_n^{DPPC} , on x_p for DPPC monolayers upon the incorporation of (■) C_{Soot} , (■) C_{Eth} , and (■) C_{Ben} . The lines are
 446 guides for the eyes. The results are the average of three individual experiments with a standard deviation smaller than
 447 5%.
 448

449 The existence of hysteresis is related to the non-efficient re-spreading of material at the interface
 450 [72]. In fact, being the lipids strongly hydrophobic molecules, they may be squeezed out from the
 451 monolayer, during the compression, forming three-dimensional aggregates or vesicles. Such
 452 aggregates tend to re-spread at the water/vapor interface during the expansion of the interface.
 453 However, the kinetics associated with the re-incorporation of the material at the interface and its
 454 re-spreading are slower than the expansion, which in turn leads to hysteresis in the traces of the Π –
 455 A/A_0 curves. This may be understood considering that packed molecules undergo a delayed re-
 456 spreading during the expansion because viscous aspects occurring when the molecules unravel each
 457 other, which makes them unable to follow the barrier rate. It should be noted that under equilibrium

458 conditions it may be expected a complete re-spreading of the material at the interface, and hence a
 459 new reduction of the available area for the monolayer will lead to a new isotherm which overlaps
 460 with the obtained during the first compression. It should be noted that the ability for response to
 461 compression-expansion cycles, and the ability for ensuring the re-spreading of material at the
 462 interface after the squeezing-out occurring during the compression are to fundamental aspects on
 463 the biophysical function of lung surfactant [20].

464 The evaluation of the impact of the incorporation of particles in the hysteresis during the whole
 465 compression–expansion cycle may provide additional information about the worsening of the
 466 mechanical properties of the DPPC monolayer as result of the incorporation of carbonaceous
 467 particles. This may be analyzed by the introduction of the normalized hysteresis area, HA_n , defined
 468 as [73]

$$HA_n = \frac{HLA}{A_{max} - A_{min}}, \quad (7)$$

469 with A_{max} and A_{min} being the maximum and minimum areas of the compression-expansion cycle,
 470 respectively, and HLA is the area of the hysteresis loop defined as follows

$$HLA = \left[\int_{A_{min}}^{A_{max}} \Pi(A) dA \right]_C - \left[\int_{A_{min}}^{A_{max}} \Pi(A) dA \right]_E, \quad (8)$$

471 where $\Pi(A)$ denotes the temporal surface pressure corresponding to the surface area A . The
 472 subindexes E and C are referred to the surface expansion and compression, respectively. The use of
 473 the HA_n provides a quantification of the effect of the particles incorporation in the refinement
 474 process of the monolayer. Figure 4b shows the dependences of the values of HA_n on x_p for DPPC
 475 monolayers upon the incorporation of different types of carbonaceous particles (Note that the
 476 values of HA_n appears normalized for the value corresponding to monolayers of DPPC spread at
 477 the water/vapor interface, HA_n^{DPPC}). The introduction of carbonaceous particles leads to a dose
 478 dependence enhancement of the hysteresis in relation to that what was found in monolayers of pure
 479 DPPC at the water/vapor interface, i.e. particles made broader the hysteresis loop. This indicates
 480 that the re-spreading of the expelled material during the compression becomes less efficient in
 481 presence of carbonaceous particles, which may be deleterious for the integrity of the lipid layers,
 482 and their protective role. The enhancement of the hysteresis may be understood considering that
 483 together to the molecules of DPPC that are expelled from the interface upon compression forming
 484 aggregates, some additional DPPC molecules are also expelled from the interface adsorbed onto the
 485 surface of carbon particles. This leads to a strong reduction of the number of DPPC molecules
 486 available at the fluid phase leads, which makes the re-spreading a less effective process [74].

487 **Quasi-Equilibrium Elasticity.** The ability of the monolayer for storing elastic energy when it is
 488 compressed under quasi-static conditions can be evaluated in terms of the quasi-equilibrium
 489 elasticity, ε . This informs about the rigidity of the monolayer upon quasi-static uniaxial
 490 compression [75]. For an isothermal compression in the Langmuir trough, the quasi-equilibrium
 491 elasticity can be obtained by the numerical derivative of the $\Pi - A$ isotherm as

$$\varepsilon = -A \left(\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial A} \right)_T. \quad (9)$$

492 The quasi-equilibrium elasticity for the different mixed monolayers is reported in Figure 5. The
 493 elasticity curve for DPPC presents two maxima, with the maximum appearing at the lowest surface

494 pressure values being ascribable to the LE phase. This phase is characterized by relatively low
 495 values of the elasticity due to its intrinsic disorder. On the other side, the second maximum is
 496 characterized by higher values of the elasticity, appearing a high surface pressures values. This
 497 maximum is associated with the formation of highly ordered LC phase. The coexistence region of
 498 DPPC monolayers is characterized in the elasticity curve for the emergence of a region with a quasi-
 499 null value of the elasticity.

500
 501 **Figure 5.** ϵ_0 - Π curves for DPPC Langmuir monolayers upon the incorporation of different weight fractions of
 502 particles at the interface (x_p): C_{Soot} (a), C_{Eth} (b) and C_{Ben}. Each curve corresponds to DPPC monolayers with a different
 503 weight fraction of particles at the interface (x_p): (■) 0.00, (■) 0.10, (■) 0.33, and (■) 0.75. The lines are guides for the
 504 eyes. The results were obtained from the average of three individual experiments with a standard deviation smaller
 505 than 5%.

506 The introduction of carbon particles modifies the feature of the elasticity in relation to that found
 507 for the pure DPPC monolayer as it may be expected from the analysis of the isotherm. The
 508 introduction of particles does not result in a significant modification of the elasticity of the LE phase.
 509 This may be explained considering the intrinsic disorder of this phase, and the limited importance
 510 of the van der Waals cohesive interaction between the lipid tails occurring at such reduced packing.
 511 However, the incorporation of particles leads to a strong reduction of the elasticity of the LC phase
 512 in relation to that what was observed for DPPC layers. This can be ascribed to the formation of
 513 composite layers, which leads to the reduction of the number of cohesive van der Waals interactions
 514 between the lipid molecules, and hence the cohesion between lipids along the monolayer is also
 515 reduced. It should be noted that the increase on the amount of particles incorporated within the
 516 interface enhances the cohesive interactions between particles and between particles and lipid
 517 molecules. However, the average cohesion within the interfacial layer is weakened. Furthermore,
 518 the shifting of the maximum for the elasticity of LC to lower values of Π with the increase of the weight
 519 fraction of particles is associated with a faster advancement on the interfacial packing of the mixed
 520 monolayers due to the increase of the total interfacial concentration.

521 Moreover, the results show that the introduction of particles hinders the phase coexistence between
 522 LE and LC phases of pure DPPC (disappearance of the region with quasi-null elasticity). Figure 6a
 523 shows the dependence of the maximum values of the elasticity for the LE and the LC phases on the
 524 weight fraction of particles.

525 The elasticity of the LE remains almost unaltered upon the incorporation of nanoparticles as was
 526 above discussed. However, the situation is quite different when the LC is considered. The presence
 527 of nanoparticles induces the decrease of the values of ϵ_0 which is related to the formation of

528 composite layers (DPPC-carbon) where the cohesive van der Waals interactions between the lipid
 529 molecules are reduced. It should be noted that the reduction of the ability for forming highly
 530 condensed phases with high quasi-equilibrium elasticity at the highest values of the surface
 531 pressure may lead to adverse changes in the normal physiological performance of lung surfactant
 532 layers. Furthermore, the introduction of carbon particles leads to an increase of the value of the
 533 elasticity of the coexistence region (see Figure 6b). This may be ascribed considering that particles
 534 hinder the formation and growth of domains of the condensed phase in the matrix formed by the
 535 expanded phase, and hence there is no a true phase coexistence between both phases as was above
 536 evidenced on the bases of the surface pressure-area isotherms.

537

538 **Figure 6. (a)** Dependence of the maximum values of the quasi-equilibrium elasticity on x_p for the LE (solid squares) and
 539 LC (solid circles) phases of DPPC monolayers upon the incorporation of (■, ●) C_{Soot} , (■, ●) C_{Eth} , and (■, ●) C_{Ben} . **(b)**
 540 Dependence of the values of the quasi-equilibrium elasticity on x_p for the LE-LC phase coexistence of DPPC monolayers
 541 upon the incorporation of (■) C_{Soot} , (■) C_{Eth} , and (■) C_{Ben} . The lines are guides for the eyes and the results were obtained
 542 from the average of three individual experiments with a standard deviation smaller than 5%.

543 **Effect of Carbon Nanoparticles in the Low frequency viscoelastic properties of DPPC**

544 **monolayers.** The dilational viscoelasticity versus frequency has been measured by the oscillatory
 545 barrier method at a fixed deformation amplitude within the linear response regime (1% of the initial
 546 area) at different degrees of compression of the monolayers [76]. This type of experiments can
 547 provide important information related to the relaxation mechanisms associated with the re-
 548 equilibration of the lipid layer as a result of the incorporation of particles, relying on the
 549 measurements of the frequency (ν) dependences of the viscoelastic modulus ($|\epsilon|$) for pure DPPC
 550 monolayers and upon the incorporation of the particles is performed. Figure S2 (see Supporting
 551 Material) shows a set of selected curves displaying the dependence of the modulus of the dilational
 552 viscoelasticity, $|\epsilon|$, on the deformation frequency, ν , at different values of reference Π for DPPC
 553 monolayers upon the incorporation of different amounts of carbonaceous particles. It should be
 554 noted that the value of the dilational viscoelastic modulus corresponding to the lowest frequency
 555 may be considered equivalent to the quasi-equilibrium elasticity, with its characteristic frequency
 556 being equivalent to the compression rate $du/dt = (dA/dt)/A = 3 \times 10^{-5}$ Hz.

557 The existence of relaxation processes with characteristic frequencies within the investigated
 558 frequency range are evidenced by the presence of inflection points in the best fit curve. The
 559 dependences of the modulus of the dilational viscoelasticity can be well described by a theoretical

560 expression corresponding to the case of one dynamic relaxation process occurring within an
 561 insoluble interfacial layer [63,77], defined as follows

$$|\varepsilon| = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon_1^2 + \varepsilon_0^2 \lambda_1^2}{1 + \lambda_1^2}}. \quad (10)$$

562 where $\lambda_1 = \nu_1/\nu$, and ν_1 defines the characteristic frequency of the relaxation process, and ε_0 and ε_1
 563 define the low frequency and high frequency limits of the dilational viscoelastic modulus,
 564 respectively (Note that the dilational viscoelastic modulus in the low frequency limit may be
 565 considered equivalent to the quasi-equilibrium elasticity calculated from the isotherm). The best fit
 566 to Equation (10) for the different curves are reported in Figure S.2 together with the experimental
 567 data. As general trend, the introduction of nanoparticles modifies both the limit elasticities and the
 568 characteristic frequency of the relaxation processes. However, the incorporation of particles into the
 569 DPPC monolayers does not introduce any additional relaxation process in the spectrum of
 570 mechanical response of the monolayer. Figure 7 displays the dependences of the characteristic
 571 frequency of the relaxation processes existing within the monolayer on the weight fraction of
 572 incorporated carbon particles into the DPPC monolayers.

573

574 **Figure 7.** Dependence of the characteristic frequency of the interfacial relaxation on the weight fraction of
 575 carbonaceous particles (\blacksquare C_{Soot} , \blacksquare C_{Eth} , and \blacksquare C_{Ben}) incorporated into DPPC monolayers. Each panel represents
 576 experiments performed around different values of reference surface pressure: (a) $\Pi = 3$ mN/m, (b) $\Pi = 7.5$ mN/m,
 577 (c) $\Pi = 11$ mN/m, (d) $\Pi = 25$ mN/m and (e) $\Pi = 40$ mN/m. The lines are guides for the eyes and the results were
 578 obtained from the average of three individual experiments with a standard deviation smaller than 5%.

579 The incorporation of carbonaceous particles into the DPPC monolayer modifies the relaxation
 580 mechanisms of the lipid at the water/vapor interface from the lowest values of surface pressure,
 581 which can be translated to a modification of the interfacial dynamics in lung surfactant films. Thus,

582 the incorporation of carbonaceous particles leads to the emergence of a relaxation process at a Π
 583 values about 3 mN/m (LE phase for pure DPPC monolayers). This process was not found in absence
 584 of particles, at least within the explored frequency range, and may be ascribed to rearrangements of
 585 the nanoparticles along the interface. Furthermore, the decrease of the characteristic frequency of
 586 this process with the increase of the weight fraction of carbonaceous particles suggests that this
 587 process can be associated with the collective reorganization of the particles, and the slowing down
 588 of this process may be ascribed to the increase of the size of the aggregates of carbonaceous particles.
 589 The increase of the surface pressure ($\Pi \sim 7.5$ mN/m) leads to the emergence of a relaxation process
 590 for DPPC before and after the incorporation of carbonaceous particles. This process presents a
 591 characteristic frequency in the range 10^{-3} - 10^{-4} Hz, and is probably related to the formations of LC
 592 domains in the LE matrix. The origin of this process is the dynamic exchange of material between
 593 the LC phase and the LE matrix, and it is slowed down with the weight fraction of the particles,
 594 which is explained considering the hindering of the motion of the lipid molecules within the
 595 interface as the interfacial density of particles increases. A further increase of Π within the LC region
 596 leads to an increase of the characteristic frequency of the relaxation process upon the incorporation
 597 of carbonaceous particles into the DPPC monolayers. In absence of nanoparticles, this relaxation can
 598 be ascribed to the lateral reorganization of the DPPC domains along the interface. On the other side,
 599 the limited condensation of the lipids associated with the incorporation of particles makes that this
 600 relaxation can be ascribed in presence of particles to the reorganization of small DPPC aggregates
 601 or even single DPPC molecules at the interface in agreement with the higher values of the
 602 characteristic frequency in relation to that found for pure DPPC monolayers. At high condensed
 603 states ($\Pi \sim 40$ mN/m), the relaxation process does not undergo any significantly modification upon
 604 the incorporation of particles, showing values about 10^{-4} Hz independently of the particle type and
 605 concentration. This can be understood considering that for such quasi-solid monolayers, the
 606 relaxation process is associated with the rearrangement of the DPPC domains, which in presence of
 607 carbonaceous particle can be associated with more complex rearrangements involving particles and
 608 lipid molecules.

609 The evaluation of the dependence of ε_1 on x_p for fixed values of Π confirms that the introduction of
 610 carbonaceous particles reduces slightly the Π of transition between the different phases emerging
 611 in DPPC monolayers (see Figure 8). This can be understood considering that the incorporation of
 612 particles leads to a reduction of the area available for the lipid reorganization, i.e. particles behave
 613 as obstacles, which induces a prior packing of the molecules at the interface monolayer.

615 **Figure 8.** Dependences of ε_l on Π for DPPC monolayers upon the incorporation of C_{Soot} (a), C_{Eth} (b), and C_{Ben} (c). In
616 each panel the set of data corresponding to different weight fraction of carbonaceous particles are included: (■) 0,
617 (■) 0.1, (■) 0.33, and (■) 0.75. Lines are guides for the eyes and the results were obtained from the average of three
618 individual experiments with a standard deviation smaller than 5%.

619 **Effect of nanoparticles on the mechanical response of the DPPC monolayers under simulated**
620 **physiological conditions.** An important aspect related to the potential physiological implications
621 of the interaction of lipid layers with particles is associated with their response under dilational
622 stresses. It is commonly accepted that the packing degree of lipid layers in biological systems is
623 around 35-40 mN/m [78]. This section will be focused on the analysis of the response of the surface
624 pressure upon periodical changes of the interfacial area with amplitudes $\Delta A/A_0$, from 1 up 40 %, at
625 a fixed frequency of 0.05 Hz [79]. In all the cases, the increase of $\Delta A/A_0$ leads to the emergence of a
626 non-linear response in the monolayer as evidenced the results displayed in Figure S.3 (see
627 Supporting Material. Notice that the results for other monolayers are qualitatively analogous). This
628 is clear from the lacked sinusoidal character of the response upon the application of a high
629 amplitude of deformation, which appears clearer from the analysis of the response profiles in terms
630 of the Fourier spectra obtained from a Fast Fourier Transform algorithm (FFT). The FFT spectra
631 evidence the emergence of non-linearity on the response by the appearance of the overtones for
632 frequency values that are integer multiples of the fundamental frequency (Notice that for
633 monolayers with linear response, only the peaks corresponding to the fundamental frequency is
634 observed).

635 The evaluation of the non-linearity of the monolayer response can be done in terms of the Total
636 Harmonic Distortion (*THD*) defined as [80,81]

$$THD = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{k>1} \Delta\sigma_k^2}}{\Delta\sigma_1}. \quad (11)$$

637 with $\Delta\sigma_k$ and $\Delta\sigma$ being the k-Fourier coefficient, i.e. the amplitude of each k-order overtone in the
638 representation of the signal as a Fourier sum, and the amplitude of the fundamental frequency,
639 respectively. *THD* allows one to represent the non-linearity degree of the monolayer response as a
640 function of the amplitude of the different harmonics of the Fourier spectrum. Thus, linear systems
641 present a response with a vanishing value of *THD*, whereas values above 0 are associated with the
642 emergence of non-linear response. Therefore, the *THD* is a very useful parameter for discriminating
643 and quantifying different regimes in the monolayer response. Figure 9 displays the dependence of
644 the *THD* on the amplitude of deformation for monolayers of DPPC upon the incorporation of
645 different amounts of carbonaceous particles.

646 The *TDH* value increases with the amplitude of the dilational deformation already for pure DPPC
647 but achieves a plateau for $\Delta A/A_0$ above 0.2. Instead, in presence of carbonaceous particles, a steeply
648 increase of the *THD* is found which is not level off even at the highest values of deformation
649 amplitude, and hence the *THD* upon the incorporation of particles appears larger than those found
650 for pure DPPC monolayers spread at the water/vapor interface. This indicates that the incorporation
651 of particles into the lipid monolayer enhances the non-linearity of the rheological response. In
652 particular, the enhancement of the non-linear character of the response is clear upon the
653 incorporation of high concentrations of carbonaceous particles. This can be rationalized in terms of
654 the degree of disruption that the incorporation of nanoparticles induces in the lateral packing of the
655 lipid molecules within the monolayer. In general, the emergence of a non-linear response on the
656 mechanical response of lipid monolayers may be explained considering a reduction of the efficiency
657 of the surface diffusion to ensure the redistribution of the material during the expansion step after

658 a strong variation of the interfacial area [82]. This emerges in pure DPPC monolayer as results of
 659 the presence of segregation of lipid microdomains. On the other side, the incorporation of
 660 carbonaceous particles leads to a further hindering of the surface diffusion, probably as result of the
 661 heterogeneous distribution of carbon particles and DPPC molecules within the interface [44,48].
 662 This type of effects may be critical for the normal function of lipid layers, affecting the dynamic of
 663 exchange of the molecules between the interface and the adjacent fluid in lung surfactant films.

664
 665 **Figure 9.** Total Harmonic distortion (*THD*) vs. relative dilational amplitude of the deformation for the surface
 666 pressure response to a harmonic area deformation in the range 0.01-0.4 at a fixed frequency $\nu_0 = 0.05$ Hz of DPPC
 667 monolayers upon the incorporation of C_{Soot} (a), C_{Eth} (b), and C_{Ben} (c). Each curve corresponds to different values of
 668 x_p : (■) 0, (■) 0.10, (■) 0.33, and (■) 0.75. The lines are guides for the eyes. In all the panels, the curve corresponding
 669 to DPPC is shown as a reference. The results were obtained from the average of three individual experiments with
 670 a standard deviation smaller than 5%.

671 A further understanding on the effect of the incorporation of carbonaceous particles in the response
 672 against mechanical perturbations of the interfacial area can be reached by introducing the stability
 673 index (SI) of the oscillatory response [83], defined as

$$SI = 2 \frac{\Pi_{min} - \Pi_{max}}{\Pi_{max} + \Pi_{min}} \quad (12)$$

674 with Π_{max} and Π_{min} being referred to the maximum and minimum values of surface pressure
 675 achieved during a sequence of compression-expansion cycles of the interfacial area. SI provides
 676 information related to the modification of the maximum amplitude of the surface pressure response
 677 upon periodical compression-expansion deformations of the interface in relation to its arithmetical
 678 mean, giving information about the ability of the lipid monolayer to reduce the surface tension
 679 under dynamics conditions of surface oscillation. Figure 10 shows the modification of the mean SI
 680 for DPPC monolayers upon the incorporation of different amounts of carbonaceous particles for
 681 oscillatory deformations of amplitude $\Delta A/A_0 = 0.4$ and a fixed frequency of 0.05 Hz. The introduction
 682 of particles, independently of their nature, leads to a reduction of the stability of the dynamics
 683 response of the monolayer, with the decrease of SI being enhanced with the weight fraction of the
 684 particles. This may be explained considering a higher reduction of the number of lipid molecules at
 685 the interface due to their association with the carbonaceous particles in agreement with the results
 686 by Sosnowski et al. [43]. A similar explanation also accounts for the different impact of the different
 687 types of carbonaceous particles.

688

689 **Figure 10.** Average SI, over 10 compression-expansion cycles, for DPPC carbon monolayers upon the incorporation of
 690 (■) C_{Soot} , (■) C_{Eth} , and (■) C_{Ben} . The lines are guides for the eyes and the error bars indicate the deviation standard between
 691 the values obtained for the SI of the different compression-expansion cycles. The results were obtained from the average of
 692 of three individual experiments with a standard deviation smaller than 5%.

693 Conclusions

694 The effect of the incorporation of three different types of carbonaceous particles on the interfacial
 695 properties of DPPC monolayers spread at the water/vapor interface has been evaluated by *in vitro*
 696 tests which provides information about the impact of carbonaceous particles in the mechanical
 697 properties of lipid layers under static and dynamics conditions, which may provide a very
 698 preliminary information related to the modification of the normal physiological function of lipid
 699 structures by measuring the compression Π -A isotherms and the response of the surface pressure
 700 to harmonic variations of the interfacial area. Thus, it possible to evaluate the potential toxicity of
 701 carbonaceous pollutants upon interaction with mammal lipid barriers, including the lung surfactant
 702 film.

703 The effect of carbonaceous particles in the interfacial properties of DPPC monolayers is governed
 704 by a combination of excluded area effect induced by the incorporation of particles into the lipid
 705 layer, and the hydrophobic interactions between the lipid molecules and the carbonaceous particles.
 706 This leads to a strong modification of both the equilibrium properties of the DPPC monolayer and
 707 their response against dilational deformation rheological due to the hindrance to the packing of the
 708 lipid molecules at the interface. This reduces the cohesion of the film, and the refinement process of
 709 the monolayer, which modifies the re-spreading kinetics of the material during the expansion of the
 710 interface. Therefore, the combination of excluded area effect and hydrophobic interactions disrupt
 711 the distribution of material within the interfaces and modify their lipid compositions. It should be
 712 noted that the reported modifications may be considered as a potential source of different
 713 dysfunctions of the normal respiratory activity when the inhalation of particles is considered.

714 The here investigated carbonaceous particles are a good representation of those ejected to the
 715 environment during combustion processes, and hence the above discussed results may have
 716 important implications for the assessment of the potential toxicological effects of carbonaceous
 717 particles upon their interaction with lipid films, e.g. tear film, skin, or lung surfactant. Besides the
 718 specific results, this study offers interesting perspectives on the developing of *in vitro* toxicology
 719 assays dealing with the response of lipid layers. In particular, the use of quantitative parameters to
 720 evaluate the effect of particles on the surface pressure response under static and dynamics

721 conditions may be a very promising tool for ranking particles in relation to their potential adverse
722 effects on mammals. However, it is necessary to deepen on the potential effect of specific chemistry
723 of the particles on the control of their impact on the interfacial properties of lipid layers.

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735 **Supporting Information:** The Supporting Information is available free of charge at
736 <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/> . Physico-chemical characteristics of the particles; surface pressure-area
737 isotherms for different types of carbon particles at the water/vapor interface; examples of traces for
738 deformation and stress response for oscillatory barriers experiments within the regions of linear and
739 non-linear response; examples of FFT spectra of stress response for oscillatory barriers experiments
740 within the regions of linear and non-linear response; representative curves of the dependences of
741 the viscoelastic modulus on deformation frequency.

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Supporting Information for “Langmuir films for a preliminary evaluation of the toxicity of carbonaceous pollutants in lipid membranes”

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S.1. Experimental details

S.1.1. Physico-chemical characteristics of particles

Table S.1 reports some relevant physico-chemical characteristic of the used carbonaceous particles (Table S.1). Further details on the particle characterization can be found in the works by Santini et al. [1,2].

Table 1. Physico-chemical characteristics of the carbonaceous particles used as pollutant models.

Particles	BET Surface area (m ² /g)	<i>d</i> ¹ (nm)
C _{Soot}	319	20-25
C _{Eth}	120	35-40
C _{Ben}	215	20-25

¹ *d* is referred to the diameter of the primary particles. The three carbons form chain-like aggregates as was observed by Transmission Electronic Microscopy [1,2].

S.2. Results

S.2.1. Study of Langmuir monolayers of carbonaceous particles spread at the bare water/vapor interface.

The hydrophobic character of the carbonaceous particles suggests that they may form monolayers upon spreading at a bare water/vapor interface, i.e. they leads to the formation of particle-laden interfaces. Therefore, as a preliminary step for obtaining a better understanding of the interaction of carbonaceous particles with DPPC layers, it is necessary to evaluate the incorporation of the carbonaceous particles at the bare water/vapor interface, in terms of their surface pressure (Π)-area (A) isotherms. Figure 1 displays the Π - A isotherms for the three different types of carbonaceous particles studied in this work (commercial Carbon Soot, C_{Soot}, and two carbon derived from combustion processes, the first one from the combustion of an ethylene flame, C_{Eth}, and the second from the combustion of a benzene flame, C_{Ben}) spread at the bare water/vapor interface.

Figure S1. Π - A/A_0 isotherms for Langmuir monolayers of the three types of carbonaceous nanoparticles studied in this work. Each curve corresponds to a different type of carbonaceous particles: (■) C_{Soot}, (■) C_{Eth}, and (■) C_{Ben}. The results were obtained from the average of three individual experiments with a standard deviation smaller than 5%.

From the isotherms of the carbonaceous particles, it is clear that they do not impact significantly on the surface tension of the bare water/vapor until their interfacial density

is large enough to form a highly packed film, which leads to the increase of the surface pressure of the monolayer. These results agree with that previously reported for monolayers of other hydrophobic particles (carbon black and fumed silica) spread at a bare water/vapor interface [3].

S.2.2. Dilational rheology

For obtaining information on the characteristic relaxation frequency from the dependences of the viscoelastic modulus on the deformation frequency, the experimental data can be analyzed in terms of a model considering the existence of an interfacial relaxation process in an insoluble film, which defines the frequency dependence of the viscoelastic dilational modulus as [4]

$$|E| = \left[\frac{\varepsilon_0^2 + \lambda^2 \varepsilon_1^2}{1 + \lambda^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (\text{S5})$$

where $\lambda = \nu_R/\nu$, with ν_R being the characteristic relaxation frequency, and ε_0 and ε_1 are the low and high frequency limits of the dilational viscoelastic modulus within the explored frequency range, respectively. Figure S.2 shows a set of selected curves displaying the dependence of the modulus of the dilational viscoelasticity, $|\varepsilon|$, on the deformation frequency, ν , at different values of reference Π for DPPC monolayers upon the incorporation of different amounts of carbonaceous particles. It should be noted that the value of the dilational viscoelastic modulus corresponding to the lowest frequency may be considered equivalent to the quasi-equilibrium elasticity, with its characteristic frequency being equivalent to the compression rate $du/dt = (dA/dt)/A = 3 \times 10^{-5}$ Hz.

Figure S2. Modulus of the dilational viscoelasticity against the deformation frequency as were obtained by oscillatory barrier experiments for a DPPC monolayers at $\Pi = 25$ mN/m upon the incorporation of different types of carbonaceous particles ($x_p = 0.10$): (■) DPPC, (■) C_{Soot} , (■) C_{eth} , and (■) C_{ben} . Lines represent the best fit theoretical curves according to Equation (6) and follow the same color code that the experimental data. The results were obtained from the average of three individual experiments with a standard deviation smaller than 5%.

S.2.3. Dilational rheology in the non-linear regime

Figure S.3. For DPPC (left) and DPPC+C_{soot} ($x_p=0.33$, right): (a) Π - response against area deformation for two different amplitudes of deformation ($\Delta A/A_0$): (●) 0.01 and (●) 0.4. (b) Fourier transform of Π - response for the curves shown in panel a. The results were obtained from the average of three individual experiments with a standard deviation smaller than 5%.

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